

Social

A STUDY ON EFFECTS OF YOGA AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

Christal Jeba N ^{*1}

^{*1} M.Ed. Scholar, Immanuel Arasar College of Education, India

Abstract

The article focuses on assessing facts of a study on effects of yoga and academic achievement of high school students'. Transcendental meditation reduces stress and improves academic performance mentally causes increased alertness, and the practice of yoga brings improvement in competitive performance. It is inferred from the present investigation that all the high school students have average level of effect of yoga with respect to all the background variables under study. It was proved that students under consideration scored higher grades and had lower stress level as compared to the other students who do not practice yoga.

Keywords: Yoga; Academic Achievement; Meditation.

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1. Introduction

Yoga, which is a way of life, is characterized by balance, health, harmony, and bliss meditation being part of yoga, which is the seventh limb of ashtanga Yoga -a state of alert rest as stated by Maharishi Mahesh Yogi, who founded a new technique of meditation, popularly known as transcendental meditation.

By practicing yoga, a person is supposed to reach a state of mental equanimity, where responses to favorable or unfavorable external events are well under the individual's control, and responses are moderate in intensity. The science of yoga is a powerful stream of knowledge, which enables the practitioners to achieve radiant physical health, serene mind, continues spiritual uplift, and creates the ability for harmonious social living.

Yoga through its techniques of meditation, asanas, and pranayama yields a positive effect in the management of stress in adolescents. The processing of sensory information at the thalamic level is facilitated during the practice of pranayama and meditation.

These two practices along with physical postures (asanas), cleansing practices, devotional sessions, and lectures on the theory and philosophy of yoga were focused to bring about an improvement in the steadiness of school students following 10 days of practice. This improvement was believed to be due to improved eye-hand coordination, attention, concentration, and relaxation.

2. Students Improvement in Academic Achievements

Getting a good night's sleep isn't as easy as going out and buying a fancy hybrid mattress that can relieve muscle pain. One way that a lot more people are sleeping better is by practicing yoga before bedtime-this is called Yogic Sleep. It is very similar to meditation, but there some slight differences that you'll notice. In general, yoga has a lot of physical benefits which include:

Increased muscle tone and strength, balanced metabolism, improved cardio and circulatory health, injury protection, improved athletic performance, improved respiration, improved energy, improved vitality, weight reduction, stress reduction, sleep inducing, relaxes the mind.

3. Academic Achievement

Academic achievement is an attained ability or degree of competence in school task, usually measured by standardized tests and expressed in grades or units based on norms derived from a sampling of pupils performance studies reveal that even low or moderate levels of stress can interfere with task performance Cognitive reactions of stress result in the inability to concentrate.

4. Hypotheses of the Study

- There is no significant difference in the yoga of high school students with regard to gender.
- There is no significant difference in the yoga of high school students with regard to yoga age.
- There is no significant difference in the yoga of high school students with regard to locality.
- There is no significant difference in the yoga of family income of high school students with regard to yoga.

5. Methodology

Sample consists of 300 IX standard students from kaniya kumari district using random sampling technique. In order to collect the details regarding the various aspects related to the present investigation appropriate tools were used a sample of 300 high school students (IX std) were selected from different schools of kaniya kumari district to them personal data sheet, and achievement test were administered

For the analysis of data following statistical techniques were used

- 1) Pearson's product moment correlation.
- 2) Significance of difference between two r 's
- 3) "t"-test
- 4) "F"-test

- 5) The investigator discussed with guide and prepared a tool to measure academic achievements of the students each statement consists of two different options they are agree and disagree

Scoring procedures

Option	Score
Agree	1
Disagree	0

6. Research Findings

Analysis and interpretation of data means subjecting the numerical data or statistical analysis leading to testing of hypotheses and arriving at findings and conclusions. It involves breaking down existing complex factor into simpler parts and putting the parts together in new arrangements for the purpose of interpretation. The generalizations drawn on the basis of research finding should be in agreement with the facts and should not conflict with the known laws of nature.

Comparison of effect of yoga and academic achievement respect to their Mother occupation

	Mother occupation	N	Mean	Std Deviation	F-VALUE	P-VALUE	R
Academic achievement	House wife	219	17.80	2.330	1.609	.202	NS
	Business	40	18.05	1.467			
	Employee	41	18.44	1.656			
	Total	300	17.92	2.158			

From the table it is clear that the P value is greater than 0.05 level of significance then hence the Null Hypothesis is accepted it shows that there is no significant difference in academic achievement of IX std school students With their Mother

7. Significance of Difference of High School Student Effect of Yoga

- There is significance difference between male and female high school students in their yoga
- There is no significance difference among high school students who aged below 15, aged 12-15 and aged above 15 in their yoga
- There is no significance difference between urban and rural residing of high school students in their yoga
- There is no significance difference among high school students studying in Government Aided Private School in their yoga.
- There is no significance difference between of high school students belonging to joint and nuclear family in their yoga.
- There is no significance difference among of high school students belonging to joint and nuclear family in their yoga.

- There is no significance difference among Hindu Christian muslim high school students in their yoga.
- There is no significance difference among of high school students belonging to the communities SC/ST, BC MBC in their yoga.
- There is no significance difference among high school students family income is below 75000 75000-90000 and above 90000 in their yoga.

8. Significance of Difference of High School Student Academic Achievement

- There is significance difference between male and female high school students in academic achievement
- There is no significance difference among high school students who aged below 15, aged 12-15 and aged above15 in academic achievement
- There is no significance difference between urban and rural residing of high school students in academic achievement
- There is no significance difference among high school students studying in Government Aided Private school in academic effect of yoga
- There is no significance difference between of high school students belonging to joint and nuclear family in academic achievement
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- There is no significance difference among high school students family income is below 75000 75000-90000 and above 90000 in their academic achievement.

9. Educational Implications

Based on the findings, the investigator stated certain educational implications.

- Make the students to develop positive attitude tribal and costal area students towards their studies. Then only they can achieve success in their academic aspects.
- Give homework and project to improve the student's science knowledge.
- Teachers should take necessary care towards their students to keep better effect of yoga among students.
- Teachers spend most of his/ her time in close relation with the students and guide them to good educational endeavors.

10. Conclusion

The results of this study are encouraging. After examination of the results, it can be determined that daily yoga participation assists in maintaining high levels of engagement and academic achievement in students. Ensuring students are aware of the expectations for positive classroom engagement and an understanding of how to participate in academic assessments is vital to the

success of the intervention. Participants in this study showed increased engagement during the second intervention over the initial baseline data collection. Due to varying participant scores, it is inconclusive if daily yoga had a strong effect on student academic achievement. Data did show high scores in the final intervention phase for all participants for academic achievement.

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